

Parallel Processing: An Insight into Architectural Modeling and Efficiency

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Abstract: *An individual uniprocessor system performs a task by its own only and does all the pipelined processes in sequence. When one talks about a parallel system, it consists of more than one processors or more than one systems connected in parallel those perform a task by dividing them in subtasks and processing each of these sub tasks on different processor/system and for this different models are proposed. In this paper we are going to enlighten the models of parallel computing and facts because of which selection of parallelism becomes much beneficial than choosing a stand-alone uniprocessor machine. We discuss the working mechanism and architecture of parallel system to go into understanding that how it works.*

Keywords: Parallelism, SISD Computers, SIMD Computers, MISD Computers, MIMD Computers, SM SIMD Computers, Interconnection Network SM SIMD Computers.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Computer is an integrated device consisting of electronic, mechanical, electrical, optical and magnetic components, used to perform calculations and operations with speed, accuracy and efficiency. The term we use as 'computer' is concerned with automation of processes once defined in it. When a task is submitted to a computer system, processor inside it is responsible for processing the task. In a uniprocessor machine a given task is processed wholly by the processor present in the system to which task is submitted.

A Parallel system is a system which is having more than one processors, able to work concurrently. When a task is submitted to such a system, task is broken down into number of subtasks and these subtasks are assigned to different processors available in it to get processed. Once when all these subtasks are processed by different processors then are integrated together to produce final outcome. This process of breaking a task into subtasks and solving them separately is called **Parallelism**. All the

processors present in a parallel system may participate in processing [1][2].

By this discussion we can come to the comparison that definitely parallel systems work much faster than a uniprocessor stand-alone system. Type of processing is also an issue because if the nature of task is not able to take advantage of parallel processing then its processing on a parallel system will reflect same circumstances as of a uniprocessor stand-alone system. But still efficiency of a parallel system in worst scene also is equivalent to the best efficiency of a uniprocessor stand-alone system [1].

The reason behind efficiency of a parallel system is not limited up to the theme of division of task only but is hidden in its architecture and synchronization with memory, other processors and control as well [1][2].

2. PARALLEL COMPUTATIONAL MODELS

Any computer either sequential or parallel; performs processing by executing the instructions on given data. A stream consisting of instructional steps (called algorithm) guides the computer that what should be done at each step and a stream of data is processed by the stream of these instructional steps. On the base of number of these streams, computers can be classified into following categories [2]-

2.1 SISD Computers

This class is having the computers which are having a single processor which receives instructions from single instruction stream and applying them on a single stream of data. During computation the instruction stream generates an instruction and processor applies it on a datum of memory using data stream. Once when an instruction is received from control, finishes its work after being applied on a datum then another instruction is generated to be

applied on another datum and this process continues until desired task is completed. This type of computers exhibit serial or sequential processing and hence these systems are also known as sequential/serial/stand-alone uniprocessor systems and shown in figure 1 [2].

Figure 1 An SISD Computer

2.2 MISD Computers

This class is having the computers which have more than one processors and each of which is having its own control unit which issues instructions to processor to which it is concerned and a memory unit which holds data and this memory is shared among all processors. Let number of processors is N, each of which receives instructions from its respective control unit and a datum is fetched from memory then datum is processed on different processors simultaneously based on the instructions they get from their respective control unit. Thus if more than one operations are to be performed on single datum at the same time then it is possible in this category as each operations can be performed on datum by a different processor and hence parallelism can be achieved [2].

This architecture gives the acceptance of data for processing in its natural form as shown in figure 2 [2].

Figure 2 An MISD Computer

2.3 SIMD Computers

This class is also having the computers which have more than one processors and each of which is having its own local memory unit in which it can store its data and programs and a common instruction stream which generates instructions and all processors are controlled by this control unit. In this model each processor can hold an individual copy of data or program in its local memory and all the copies held by processors can be identical with no issues [2].

The processors work synchronously as at each step and same instruction is executed by all the processors on each datum. The instruction can either be simple or complex. In the same way data can also be simple or complex. Sometimes, it becomes compulsory to assign the task of

processing to a particular subset of processors. This information can be associated by being encoded so that it should be known that when a particular processor should be *active* or *inactive*. Activation means a processor is allowed to execute the instruction and inactivation means a processor has to wait for next instruction. There is a provision which can be called a global clock which ensures clock-synchronized operations. There may be a time interval between executions of instructions as there may be processors those have completed their execution of current instruction before others complete their execution or they are in the current set of execution participants. This interval of time can either be definite or indefinite or it may also depend on currently executing instruction. An SIMD computer can be viewed as shown in figure 3 [2].

Figure 3 An SIMD Computer

One of the most flashed aspects is communication among processors. In order to exchange their data or intermediate results they can be in either of two types – SM (Shared Memory) and interconnection Network, discussed below.

2.3.1 SM SIMD Computers

This category is also known as **Parallel Random Access Machine (PRAM)** in field of parallel computation. In this model all parallel processors use a common memory and if two processors want to communicate, they do so by using this shared memory. If a processor x wants to send datum to processor y then this process will be done in two steps – first, processor x writes datum to a memory location of shared memory which location is known to y; second, processor y reads that datum which is previously written by x.

During the execution of any parallel algorithm all the parallel processors get access to a shared memory for their read and write operations simultaneously. If memory locations being used by these processors are distinct then concurrent access takes place but if the memory locations are same those are to be accessed by multiple processors then certain issues may arise. Hence following categories

of SM SIMD Computers come in the picture to resolve this read/write conflicts of processors [2].

2.3.1.1 EREW SM SIMD Computers

This class of SM SIMD computers is called **Exclusive Read Exclusive Write SM SIMD** computers. This class does not allow more than one processors to access same memory location for their read/write operations at the same time. At a time only one processor is allowed to use a specific memory location and hence this class provides only exclusive use of memory among processors.

2.3.1.2 CREW SM SIMD Computers

This class of SM SIMD computers is called **Concurrent Read Exclusive Write SM SIMD** computers. This class allows more than one processors to read from same memory location concurrently but writing is still exclusive i.e. only one processor is allowed to perform write operation to a memory location at a time.

2.3.1.3 ERCW SM SIMD Computers

This class of SM SIMD computers is called **Exclusive Read Concurrent Write SM SIMD** computers. This class allows more than one processors to write into the same memory location concurrently but reading is still exclusive i.e. only one processor is allowed to perform read operation from a memory location at a time.

2.3.1.4 CRCW SM SIMD Computers

This class of SM SIMD computers is called **Concurrent Read Concurrent Write SM SIMD** computers. This class allows more than one processors to write into the same memory location at the same time and it allows concurrent read operation also i.e. more than one processors are allowed to read from the same memory location at same time [2].

Allowing concurrent read has no issues because all the processors read content from the same location of shared memory concurrently and store a copy of content into their local memory and use it whenever required. Fetching element from central memory takes bit more time whereas retrieval from own local memory is bit faster.

When the turn of concurrent writing comes then certain issues arise as if multiple processors attempt to write to the same memory location then data written by one processor may overwrite data previously written by another processor. This scenario is called write conflict which arises in two categories – ERCW and CRCW. Certain policies are adopted to resolve write conflicts as-

(a). The processor with smallest label of number is permitted to write and rest of the processors are not allowed to access that memory location till smallest numbered processor finishes its operation.

(b). All processors having data of equal amount are allowed to write otherwise all the processors are prohibited from access to memory location.

(c). Total sum of all the data is written to a memory location for which all the processors are attempting to write [2].

SM SIMD model describes the way to make parallel processing more efficient and feasible by dividing the memory in form of regions and making use of these regions exclusive. This theme can be improved and made more powerful in Interconnection Network SIMD model.

2.3.2 Interconnection Network SIMD Computers

This model introduces the idea of distribution of shared memory. The idea is that say there are total P processors and shared memory is having M memory locations so each processor is having M/P memory locations. During any step of execution processor P_x should be able to receive a datum from another processor P_y and P_x should also be able to send a datum some other processor P_z . The whole exchange of data is depending on level of interconnection of processors. The factors required for this model are –

(a). A circuit whose cost is $C(P-1)$ and it should be able to decode $\log(P-1)$ -bit address. This makes a processor P_x able to communicate with rest P-1 processors in interconnection.

(b). A circuit with cost $C(M/P)$ which should be able to decode $\log(M/P)$ -bit address received from other processors.

An Interconnection Network Model is more powerful than Shared Memory model because it provides instant interaction between any pair of processors and thus many pairs of processors can communicate simultaneously. An interconnection network is shown in figure 4 in which each processor is connected with all other processors [2].

Figure 4 An interconnected network

Different interconnection networks are thought and designed to work with specific infrastructures. Major interconnection networks are listed below:

1. Interconnection as Linear Array
2. Interconnection as Two Dimensional Array or mesh
3. Interconnection as Tree
4. Perfect Shuffle Interconnection
5. Interconnection as Cube

2.4 MIMD Computers

This is most efficient and powerful model of parallel computation as it is having N processors, N data streams and N instruction streams. Each processor runs under the control of instruction stream of its own control unit over the data of its own data stream as shown in figure 5 [2].

Figure 5 An MIMD Computer

So in this model all the processors are having their separate control unit and memory unit. Thus different processors operate on different data under their instruction stream simultaneously. Hence it can be said that all the processors in MIMD model work asynchronously.

Communication between processors is done either by a shared memory or by an interconnection network. The MIMD computers using a shared memory are also called multiprocessor computers or tightly coupled computers and the MIMD computers using interconnection network are so called as multicomputer system or loosely coupled systems [2].

3. ISSUES IN PARALLEL PROCESSING

While dealing with parallel systems many aspects should be taken care and certain issues are also there to be resolved. In this section we are going to discuss major issues in parallel processing as follows [8] –

- (i). Data management techniques should be optimized otherwise it may lead computational delays as improper management makes retrieval of desired data tedious [3].
- (ii). Instrumentation is always an issue because wrong selection of equipment, improper structuring or improper instrumentation improves the delays in processing, hence appropriate instrumentation is required [3].
- (iii). Excellent resource management is required so that resources should be optimally utilized and participate in overall speed up [3].
- (iv). Efficient algorithms are required so that they can match the efficiency of infrastructure and speed up the process by supporting hardware [4][5].

(v). Communication mechanism should be managed and systematized in such a way that it should be feasible and efficient equivalent to the algorithm and equipments being used.

(vi). Efficiency of processors being used should be monitored because one uses parallel computer for the sake of increased speed and the best efficiency he/she can get. Therefore if multiple processors are going to be used then there efficiency should match the overall performance measure otherwise it will not be worthwhile [9].

4. APPLICATIONS OF PARALLEL PROCESSING

As the use of computers is not limited up to any specific area, parallelism is also the concept being widely used. Wherever a need of more speeded and efficient processing arise, theme of parallelism is used. At present among the wide use of parallelism we are going to mention some major area of applications of parallelism and its variations [6][7][10]–

1. Distributed Processing
2. Cloud computing
3. Networked Processing
4. Wireless network processes
5. Processing on Grids
6. Environmental studies
7. Geological studies
8. Scientific researches
9. Neural networks
10. Training Machines
11. Bio-informatics
12. Commercial applications
13. Stock market
14. Banking
15. Residential Information Systems

5. CONCLUSIONS

As we have discussed that a parallel system is more efficient than a uniprocessor stand-alone machine because of its way to deal with processing methodologies and its architectural design so if it is required to process a large amount of data then selection of a parallel machine is always beneficial than a stand-alone uniprocessor machine. We discussed how parallel systems take advantage of their design and distribution of task to be performed on data under the control of specified instruction stream so that multiple processors can be able to work simultaneously on data. Therefore for increased and efficient processing a Parallel system is always better. Depending on the hardware equipments being used and efficiency of algorithm to be implemented the overall efficiency of a parallel system can be measured.

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the work efficiency of equipments used in parallel systems to enhance the work ability of it and our grateful thanks to the contributors who introduced the processes and procedures to improve speed of parallel processing as overall performance depends on both hardware and software components.

profession he worked with C, C++, C#, Data structures and algorithms, Database Systems, Bluetooth Technology, Clouds and Parallel Processing.

References

- [1] Jehad A. AI-Sadi, "Broadcasting and Routing Algorithms for the Extended OTIS-Cube Network", *International Journal of Communications* Issue 3, Volume 5, 2011
- [2] S. G. AkL "The Design and Analysis of Parallel Algorithms", Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1989.
- [3] Luiz A. DeRose, Mario Pantano, Daniel A. Reed, Jeffery S. Vetter, "Performance Issues in Parallel Processing Systems", [www.http://www-pablo.cs.uiuc.edu/](http://www-pablo.cs.uiuc.edu/), USA.
- [4] ADVE, V., Mellor-Crummey, J., Wang, J.-C., and Reed, D., "Integrating Compilation and Performance Analysis For Data Parallel Programs", *Proceeding of Supercomputing'95* (November 1995).
- [5] William D. Gropp, "Issues in Accurate and Reliable Use of Parallel Computing in Numerical Programs", The manuscript created by university of Chicago as operator of Argonne National Laboratory under contract with U.S. Department of Energy, Aug 27, 2004.
- [6] R. H. Bisseling, "Parallel Scientific Computation: A Structured Approach Using BSP and MPI", Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, March 2004.
- [7] Jan Kwiatkowski, "Evaluation of Parallel Programs by Measurement of Its Granularity", R. Wyrzykowski et al. (Eds.): PPAM 2001, LNCS 2328, pp. 145–153, 2002. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2002.
- [8] Sartaj Sahni and Venkat Thanvantri, "Parallel Computing: Performance Metrics and Models", Computer & Information Sciences Department, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611, USA. A work supported in part by the Army Research Office under grant DAA H04-95-1-0111.
- [9] Mounir Hamdi, Yi Pan, B. Hamidzadeh, F. M. Lim, "Parallel Computing on an Ethernet cluster of workstations: Opportunities and constraints", *The Journal of supercomputing*, 12, 111-132(1999).
- [10] Will Eatherton, "The push of network processing to the top of the pyramid.", In *Symposium on Architectures for Networking and Communications Systems*, NewJersey,USA, 2005.

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